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Building transdisciplinary bridges and learning from the Svalbard context

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the challenges and key enablers of transdisciplinary research in the specific context of Svalbard, offering methodological perspectives and recommendations. The interconnected climatic and socioeconomic changes in Svalbard call for collaboration across disciplines, as well as societal stakeholders. Such integrative research collaboration is conceptualised as a transdisciplinary approach. This approach emphasises a need for continuous and holistic knowledge co-production and relevant data-sharing across sectors, ensuring a robust foundation for informed decision-making and development strategies. However, navigating transdisciplinarity can be complex, as research often aligns with traditional disciplinary structures. This paper emerged from a collaborative exchange on how to carry out transdisciplinary research in Svalbard, a process that proved productive for transdisciplinary knowledge production. It incorporates insights from two workshops where both researchers from diverse disciplines and non-academic stakeholders actively contributed to discussions and the development of this article. Acknowledging the dynamic nature of transdisciplinary research, we present the themes that emerged from our workshops, categorised as challenges, opportunities, and best

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practices. These themes are then discussed in light of the democratic and pragmatic principles that underpin transdisciplinary research. We conclude the study by offering recommendations aimed at fostering further co-creation across disciplines and stakeholders from a transdisciplinary perspective.

Introduction

Climate change in the Arctic region is occurring faster and with a greater intensity compared to other areas.¹ This phenomenon raises urgent concerns for both human settlements and ecosystems, challenges that Svalbard faces alongside other Arctic locations. Addressing the coupled climatic, environmental, and socioeconomic changes in Svalbard require new ways of thinking and collaboration, as traditional disciplinary research alone is insufficient for achieving comprehensive understanding and establishing shared objectives.² To effectively grasp local perceptions and the impacts of these changes, as well as to identify potential decision-making solutions, it is essential to integrate both first-hand local and expert insights.³

A *transdisciplinary approach* aimed at addressing complex problems, such as climate change, is emerging as a means to define research questions and identify solutions to the associated societal and environmental challenges. Integrating diverse forms of knowledge from both academic and non-academic stakeholders is essential for developing solutions that are relevant to policymakers and society as a whole. In the Arctic context, such efforts have predominantly focused on co-producing scientific and Indigenous knowledge to address jointly defined problems.⁴ Hence, the *co-production of knowledge* among various scientific disciplines and non-academic stakeholders serves as the foundation for transdisciplinarity.⁵ In this paper, *non-academic stakeholders* are broadly defined to include individuals, groups, local and expert knowledge holders, organisations, and interest groups that are either part of or have a vested interest in the community.

Numerous examples of successfully implemented transdisciplinary projects can be found throughout the Arctic. One instance is an ongoing collaboration involving academia (the Institute of Oceanography), industry (the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators, or AECO), an NGO (Oceans North), the local Indigenous government (Nunatsiavut Government), and an Indigenous community (*Mittimatalik* Hunter and Trappers Organization). This partnership is generating crucial knowledge regarding the marine environment, particularly concerning legislation and data related to underwater noise pollution in the Canadian Arctic.⁶ Another is the Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program, which brings together international scientists, governments, Indigenous organisations, and conservation groups to monitor and assess the health of Arctic ecosystems.

¹Rantanen et al., *The Arctic Has Warmed*, 1–10.

²Nyseth and Viken, "Communities of Practice," 66–75.

³Eicken et al., "Connecting Top-down and Bottom-up Approaches," 467–483.

⁴Doering et al., "Improving the relationships,"

⁵Lang et al., *Transdisciplinary Research*, 25–43.

⁶Jones et al., "Impact of ship noise," 1–17.

However, transdisciplinary approaches that promote the co-production of knowledge between academic and non-academic stakeholders present challenges that have yet to be fully explored in the context of Svalbard. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by exploring the following question: What are the key considerations for successfully conducting transdisciplinary research in Svalbard?

To answer this question, our methodological approach involved three sets of qualitative data, including literature review, the outcomes of two workshops, and participants' essays on personal experiences with transdisciplinary projects related to Svalbard and the Arctic. For the workshop we convened a diverse group of scientists from various disciplines engaged in Svalbard research alongside non-academic stakeholders relevant to the region. The participants were asked to share their experiences in form of essays and engaged in discussions about transdisciplinarity within the Svalbard context. Collectively, we examined the challenges and opportunities associated with initiating and conducting transdisciplinary research, as well as the processes of knowledge sharing and co-production. Both academic and non-academic stakeholders participated as co-authors of this article. Additionally, we conducted a scoping literature review to clarify the primary terms used in transdisciplinary research. For example, the literature uses the terms *stakeholders* and *actors* interchangeably.

This article begins by outlining the aims, rationale, and concept of transdisciplinarity, including its advantages and disadvantages. We then present the context of Svalbard-related research and elaborate on the data collection methods employed in this study. Following this, we provide insights from both academic and non-academic perspectives on transdisciplinary research, highlighting key considerations and offering suggestions for overcoming potential challenges. We also examine examples of successful collaborations. Guided by our research question, our discussion elaborates on these insights and concludes with recommendations for effectively conducting transdisciplinary research in the context of Svalbard.

Conceptual framework

The concept of transdisciplinarity emerged in the 1970s and is now recognised as an innovative and promising approach for generating knowledge and informing decision-making in response to environmental and societal challenges, particularly in the context of sustainability.⁷ This approach has been integrated into calls for participatory research, collaborative projects,⁸ and various conferences, such as the International Transdisciplinarity Conference. In recent years, the Research Council of Norway and other funding agencies, such as EU Horizon Europe and the Belmont Forum, have increasingly supported transdisciplinary (or 'partner') projects focused on the Arctic. These research programmes emphasise the societal impacts that arise from addressing real-world challenges.

⁷von Wehrden, *Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary*, 875–888; Pohl et al., *Conceptualising Transdisciplinary Integration*, 18–26.

⁸Bremer and Meisch, "Co-production in climate change research," 1–22.

The transdisciplinary approach is proposed as a means to respond to increasing complexity of socio-natural systems,⁹ particularly in addressing ‘wicked problems’¹⁰ such as climate change.¹¹ One widely accepted definition is provided by Lang et al.,¹² who conceptualise transdisciplinarity as:

...a reflexive, integrative, method-driven scientific principle aiming at the solution or transition of societal problems and concurrently of related scientific problems by differentiating and integrating knowledge from various scientific and societal bodies of knowledge.

Given this definition, two epistemological questions emerge: What type of knowledge can we collect to understand coupled environmental and socioeconomic changes, and whose knowledge is included to reach this understanding? In this study, the concept of knowledge is defined as ‘*what a person employs to interpret and act on the world, [including] feelings (attitudes) as well as information, embodied skills as well as verbal taxonomies and concepts: all the ways of understanding that we use to make up our experienced, grasped reality*’.¹³

The transdisciplinary approach follows a participatory research methodology, as it acknowledges the interaction and mutual learning between science and society through the knowledge co-production process.¹⁴ While there are several ways to conceptualise knowledge co-production, we align with the following definition: it is an ‘*iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways toward a sustainable future*’.¹⁵

In contrast to multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches, which bridge and integrate multiple scientific disciplines, the transdisciplinary approach goes further and integrates non-academic stakeholders in knowledge production (see [Figure 1](#)). Social scientists have long integrated the knowledge of their interlocutors into their own production of knowledge. A transdisciplinary approach extends this by treating non-academic stakeholders as full research partners, involved in all phases of research – from problem formulation and project management to funding, synthesis, and the application of results and solutions. This approach is similar to community-based research approaches, as it ideally fosters *collaboration* throughout the entire research process.¹⁶ However, while community-based research may be conducted by researchers from the same disciplinary backgrounds, transdisciplinarity requires a broader cross-disciplinary collaboration. Thus, transdisciplinarity transcends disciplinary and interdisciplinary methodological and theoretical paradigms, promoting the development of a ‘shared approach to research’.¹⁷ Whereas conventional science is often considered as producing knowledge that is ‘translated’ for societal use, transdisciplinarity advocates for understanding knowledge production as a ‘mutual learning process involving both science and

⁹von Wehrden, *Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary*, 875–888.

¹⁰Highly complex problems that involve competing interests and lack clear-cut solutions.

¹¹Serrao-Neumann, “One Human Settlement,” 97–109.

¹²Lang et al., *Transdisciplinary Research*, 26–27.

¹³Barth, *An Anthropology of Knowledge*, 1.

¹⁴Hummel, *Inter- and Transdisciplinary*, 481–509.

¹⁵Norström et al., *Principles for knowledge co-production*, 183.

¹⁶Brandt et al., *A Review of Transdisciplinary Research*, 1–15.

¹⁷Pohl, *From Transdisciplinarity to Transdisciplinary Research*, 66.

Figure 1. Various approaches to scientific research.

society'.¹⁸ This approach aims to better understand societal needs and enhance the impact of research on society.¹⁹

The transdisciplinary approach recognises and values various forms of knowledge, facilitating learning among distinct stakeholder groups and striving for research relevant to societal needs.²⁰ Non-academic stakeholders may include policymakers and decision-makers from government, industry, and the community, as well as other societal actors such as NGOs, practitioners, media representatives, and other relevant actors.²¹ The inclusion of perspectives that were historically excluded from research practices makes this approach unique.²²

However, it should also be noted that significant debate surrounds the transdisciplinary approach,²⁴ particularly regarding its credibility – encompassing epistemological and methodological choices – and its saliency, or relevance. Reconciling the diverse and sometimes conflicting interests and types of knowledge from theoretical scientists and practice-oriented stakeholders presents various challenges.²⁵ Serrao-Neumann²⁶ identifies several barriers, including structural, cognitive, and normative obstacles; differing communication styles; difficulties in framing real-world problems within a research context; and the time-consuming and emotionally taxing nature of the process. The co-production of knowledge also presents challenges within traditional institutional structures, as does the integration of a broad set of methods from different disciplines.²⁷ Project participants may lack the necessary experience and competence for effective knowledge co-production. Furthermore, non-academic participants may have varying expectations regarding the project, particularly concerning the nature of the societal impacts.²⁸

¹⁸Hummel, *Inter- and Transdisciplinary*, 481–509.

¹⁹Angelstam et al., *Solving Problems*, 254–265.

²⁰Westberg and Polk, *The Role of Learning*, 385–397.

²¹von Wehrden, *Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary*, 875–888.

²²Klein, *The Transdisciplinary Moment(Um)*, 189–199.

²³Adapted from Peek and Guikema, *Interdisciplinary Theory*, 1048.

²⁴Klenk and Mehaan, *Climate Change and Transdisciplinary*, 160–167.

²⁵Polk, *Transdisciplinary Co-Production*, 110–122.

²⁶Serrao-Neumann, *One Human Settlement*, 97–109.

²⁷Thompson et al., *Scientist and Stakeholder*, 30–39.

²⁸Brandt et al., *A Review of Transdisciplinary Research*, 1–15.

Lang et al.²⁹ further highlight the typical mutual scepticism among scientists and non-academic actors as a major challenge to collaborative research. Whereas the former might be concerned that transdisciplinarity could compromise the scientific method, thereby undermining credibility, the latter might question the applicability and relevance of results. Moreover, the success of a project may have different meanings for the parties involved. For example, non-academic stakeholders may seek long-term solutions to their real-world problems, whereas researchers are expected to deliver academic results and advance the research frontier.³⁰ The research funding cycle also limits the potential for long-term collaboration. In many ways, researchers are at the mercy of funding agencies and their underlying policies.

Additional challenges associated with transdisciplinary projects include the significant organisational costs in terms of both time and funding, as well as the difficulties involved in 'reintegrating' results into practice.³¹ Due to these challenges, the effective implementation of transdisciplinarity in research projects remains relatively rare.³² While the literature often acknowledges the complexities of knowledge co-production, it often describes the transdisciplinary process in normative terms, presenting integration – the aspiration to assimilate heterogeneous knowledge systems – as the regulative ideal. However, this 'integration imperative [...] masks the ontological politics of scientific knowledge' and 'conceals the friction, antagonism, and power inherent in knowledge co-production'.³³

To overcome these challenges, project participants are typically encouraged to adopt a transparent, reflective approach and remain open to multiple realities by acknowledging different ontologies and epistemologies.³⁴ Establishing a clear framework for the research process and developing a common terminology is also essential.³⁵ Furthermore, transdisciplinarity acknowledges that diverse perspectives can coexist through the 'weaving of knowledge systems'.³⁶ According to Westberg and Polk,³⁷ the transdisciplinary process should create a space for self-reflection and facilitate discussions about the relevance of the research, its outcomes, and the learning experiences of the involved stakeholders. Angelstam et al.³⁸ emphasise the importance of minimising disciplinary evaluations of transdisciplinary applications and reducing traditional disciplinary control. Against this conceptual backdrop, we introduce empirical examples from Svalbard.

Svalbard-related research and context – the potential for transdisciplinarity

Several 'wicked problems' have emerged within the Svalbard context, which we argue necessitate a transdisciplinary approach. Svalbard has experienced rapid climatic and environmental changes, including an increase in air temperature of 3 to 5°C over the past

²⁹Lang et al., *Transdisciplinary Research*, 25–43.

³⁰Lawrence, *Characteristics, Potentials, and Challenges*, 44–61.

³¹Polk, *Transdisciplinary Co-Production*, 110–122.

³²von Wehrden, *Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary*, 876.

³³Ibid, 160.

³⁴Lawrence, *Characteristics, Potentials, and Challenges*, 44–61.

³⁵Brandt et al., *A Review of Transdisciplinary Research*, 1–15.

³⁶Pohl et al., *Conceptualising Transdisciplinary Integration*, 18–26.

³⁷Westberg and Polk, *The Role of Learning*, 385–397.

³⁸Angelstam et al., *Solving Problems*, 254–265.

40 to 50 years, increased rainfall, and significant loss of sea ice.³⁹ These changes pose threats to the high-Arctic environment, its population, and various species, some of which are ice-dependent. Rising temperatures, along with subsequent changes in cryosphere conditions, raise urgent questions about how to best secure living conditions for Arctic residents and preserve the region's cultural heritage sites.⁴⁰

The Svalbard Treaty (1920) grants Norway 'full and absolute' sovereignty over Svalbard, while simultaneously ensuring the rights of nationals from all contracting parties to work and establish businesses on the archipelago. Consequently, Svalbard has an international population spread across the Norwegian community of Longyearbyen (with 35% non-Norwegian citizens), two Russian-speaking settlements (Barentsburg and Pyramiden), Ny-Ålesund, a Norwegian-run international research station and a Polish research station in Hornsund. The population of the Svalbard communities comprises transient settlers and researchers from around the world. Historically, many individuals were employed in the mining industry, while currently, the population includes skilled professionals such as scientists, engineers, and business-people, as well as bureaucrats, students, tour guides, and workers indispensable for the service industry. However, communities still form and function within these highly international, hyperconnected, and hypermobile locations.⁴¹ Box 1 outlines the uniqueness of Svalbard and its similarities with other Arctic regions.

Longyearbyen and, to some extent Barentsburg have experienced significant cross-scale socioeconomic changes over the past decade.⁴² In Longyearbyen, coal mining is being phased out (ceased in June 2025), while tourism, research, and education have been identified by the Norwegian government as Svalbard's economic pillars.⁴³ The town is predominantly maintained as a means to achieve a political objective—ensuring Norwegian sovereignty through its continued presence—resulting in a governance

BOX 1. Svalbard's characteristics

Shared with other Arctic locations:

- Rapid climatic and environmental changes.
- Resource frontier periphery, controlled by a distant political and economic authority.
- Reduced Arctic Sea ice expands navigable shipping routes and creates opportunities for land and sea resource extraction.
- Dependence on resource extraction as well as tourism.
- Local population with a sense of belonging, calling the place their home.

Unique to Svalbard:

- No Indigenous population. The first permanent settlements were coal-mining towns in the early 20th century.
- Transient and international communities with a high turnover.
- A unique legal framework, including the Svalbard Treaty and the Svalbard Act.
- Geopolitical situation: Svalbard is governed by Norway but attracts the attention of many actors in the global geopolitical arena.
- Strict environmental regulations effectively control any efforts to explore land-based resource extraction.

³⁹Hanssen-Bauer et al., *Climate in Svalbard*.

⁴⁰Brode-Roger, *Mining, Materiality and Memory*, 104–120.

⁴¹Olsen, *Shipping and Arctic communities*, 51–54; Meyer et al. *Communities despite transience*.

⁴²Olsen et al., *Barentsburg and Longyearbyen*.

⁴³Ministry of Justice and Public Security, *Svalbard*, 2015–2016.

structure that is largely top-down. However, in the context of coupled climatic and socioeconomic changes, maintaining control over the archipelago has become an increasingly complex task. In response, the Norwegian government has implemented stricter regulations across various areas, including tourism, research, environment protection, and demography.⁴⁴ These regulatory measures have profound consequences for Svalbard communities.

The complex political and legal conditions in Svalbard create an intriguing backdrop for conducting context-specific and locally anchored transdisciplinary research. A transdisciplinary approach to research can enhance the inclusion of diverse social groups with varying rights, cultural backgrounds, and economic circumstances, thereby advancing and integrating their tacit knowledge. This, in turn, can improve decision-making processes as stakeholders navigate these complex challenges.⁴⁵ Johannessen and Haavik⁴⁶ also argue that given the challenging climate risks in Svalbard – such as avalanches – broad knowledge production that involves individuals with expertise related to avalanche is crucial for effective decision-making.

Finally, situated within a condensed geographic space and accommodating various academic and research institutions, such as the University Center in Svalbard (UNIS), as well as local institutions like the Longyearbyen Community Council, Longyearbyen is well-positioned to facilitate transdisciplinary research efforts. These initiatives can foster enduring connections between scientific disciplines and non-academic stakeholders within the community. In this context, such collaborations do not imply bridging fundamentally different epistemologies and cosmologies, as is often the case in Indigenous contexts. The distinction between ‘locals’ and ‘experts’ is not highly relevant here, as many expert professionals and scientists reside in Svalbard. This context makes Svalbard an ideal setting for identifying bottleneck problems and developing solutions to interconnected environmental and societal challenges through transdisciplinary research processes. [Box 2](#) presents examples of Svalbard-related projects initiated and participated in by the co-authors of this paper.

Methods

To explore the challenges and key enablers of transdisciplinary research in Svalbard, this study draws on three data sets, all forming part of a collaborative knowledge-production process. The data set includes: 1) notes from two workshops focused on transdisciplinarity in Svalbard-related projects; 2) essays submitted by workshop participants and; and 3) a scoping literature review on transdisciplinarity. Taken together, these methods aim to ensure the inclusion of diverse voices, narratives, and perspectives, which is a prerequisite for transdisciplinarity. The methodology outlined below therefore proved to be a fruitful way of practicing transdisciplinarity. The adoption of this approach is operationalised through a three-stage process: preparation for the workshop, workshop activities, and data analysis.

⁴⁴Ministry of Justice and Public Security, *Svalbard*, 2023–2024.

⁴⁵Indreiten et al. *Field operations in the high Arctic*, 1939.

⁴⁶Johannessen and Haavik, *The role of local knowledge*, 417–433.

BOX 2. Svalbard-related projects that adopted a transdisciplinary approach

SVALUR (2020–2023) was a project funded by the Belmont Forum. A project team explored how scientific knowledge – generated through long-term environmental monitoring – interacts with and informs non-scientific ways of knowing, establishing an environmental memory of Svalbard. The team collaborated with local knowledge holders, including tour guides, scientists, and individuals employed in science logistics, as well as stakeholders such as the Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS).

Sustainable Tourism in Svalbard – A Balancing Act (2020–2024) was a project funded by the Research Council of Norway and focused on the action space for tourism operators in Svalbard. This initiative was co-created and executed by a team of researchers in partnership with two key tourism operators: AECO and Visit Svalbard. BalancingAct investigated how climatic and environmental changes, national regulatory frameworks, international processes, and local perceptions regarding tourism converge to shape the potential for a sustainable tourism industry. The tourism industry partners remained dedicated and involved throughout the project period, designating BalancingAct as a successful example of transdisciplinary collaboration.

PermaMeteoCommunity (2021–2024). This project involved collaboration with Longyearbyen Local County and local companies alongside scientific and engineering partners from UNIS and several Norwegian authorities and companies. The primary aim of the project was to develop a climate change-related permafrost response system, enabling authorities in Longyearbyen to directly access key data on meteorology and permafrost conditions in the town. This data is particularly valuable for preparedness against extreme events such as rainstorms or heat waves. In collaboration with the LongyearOBS project, funded by the Svalbard Environmental Fund, citizen science activities were developed to contribute data to the response system.

INTAROS (2016–2022) was an EU project aimed at strengthening and promoting community-based monitoring and citizen science in local Arctic communities. This approach directly involves Indigenous and local residents in data collection and, in some cases, interpretation, linking monitoring efforts to the decisions made by local stakeholders. In Svalbard, citizen science activities are primarily conducted by tourists and other visitors who collect observations of birds, whales, and other marine species. Expedition cruise operators also actively engage tourists in the collection of environmental data, collaborating with scientists who oversee the quality and dissemination of the data.

The preparation for the workshop started with a scoping literature review that served dual purposes. Firstly, it established a shared understanding of the concept of transdisciplinarity and how it is addressed in literature. Secondly, we used some of the findings to structure the workshop questions and frame the discussions. We selected 20 relevant scientific articles that holistically describe and critically examine a transdisciplinary approach and its application in sustainability literature. The search for articles was conducted in Google Scholar using the keywords *transdisciplinary** and *approach*, focusing on publications in English from 2010 to 2024. The following categories were selected for thematic analysis: ‘definition of the concept’, ‘rationale for applying the approach’, ‘whose knowledge is included’, and ‘primary advantages, disadvantages, and strategies for overcoming these’. Additionally, we included an open category titled: ‘notes relevant to the study’.

In addition, prior to the workshops, the participants were asked to submit individual essays which discussed the challenges and opportunities associated with transdisciplinary work in Svalbard-related projects they were involved in (see [Box 2](#)). The essays were analysed with the use of thematic categories used in literature review. The inclusion of essays helped the organisers to form the workshop questions and structure. The essays ensured that all voices were heard while also identifying potential ethical challenges and recognising asymmetric power relations that may arise during the workshops.

The co-authors of this paper participated in one or two workshops held in conjunction with the Svalbard Science Conference in October 2023 and the Arctic Congress Bodø in May 2024. Each workshop hosted 25–30 participants including researchers from multiple disciplines – such as sociology, health, anthropology, archaeology, marine biology, and

remote sensing – as well as non-academic Svalbard-related stakeholders, such as the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators, Svalbard Museum, Svalbard Folk High school, Svalbard Science Forum, and the Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System. Discussions around who to include as relevant stakeholders were framed not only as a matter of transdisciplinary but also as ethical dilemmas, emphasising the need for a plurality of voices to be represented. All invited researchers participated in Svalbard-related research projects, focusing on changes in Svalbard or in one of the three communities: Longyearbyen, Barentsburg and Ny-Ålesund.

The workshops were structured to facilitate active engagement. During the workshops the participants were divided into five groups. The first five co-authors had a responsibility to moderate the discussions in the assigned groups. The workshop discussions were not recorded, but each group was asked to write detailed post-it answers on the prepared questions. The discussed questions were: what were the necessity of transdisciplinary research, what forms of knowledge were utilised in our research, do you collaboration across disciplines and between science and society, what are barriers to data sharing and best practices for collaboration, and how transdisciplinary findings can contribute to decision-making.

The workshops' notes were thematically analysed by the moderators alongside the essays to identify themes, which were broadly categorised into 'challenges for' and 'aspects of success' for transdisciplinary research. They were further refined during the collective writing process, which included input from many of the workshop participants. The themes form the structure of the findings.

Findings

This section is shaped by our research question: What are the key considerations for successfully conducting transdisciplinary research in Svalbard? Our findings are based on our empirical data, including workshop discussions, the reflections of the workshop participants on their experiences with transdisciplinary research in Svalbard, and the collaborative writing process of this paper. The section begins by presenting the rationale behind transdisciplinary research in Svalbard and highlighting its key benefits, as identified by the workshop participants. We then summarise the potential challenges faced in this context. Finally, we conclude with a discussion of the 'aspects of success', outlining strategies to address these challenges and improve the effectiveness of transdisciplinary research in Svalbard.

The engagement of the non-academic stakeholders and scholars from various disciplines in the workshops, as well as their reflections and discussions, indicate a broad interest in transdisciplinary research in the Svalbard context. The participants shared a common belief that science must have societal relevance and agreed on the importance of involving non-academic stakeholders to identify community needs and develop effective solutions. They emphasised that addressing the environmental changes and related challenges facing Svalbard communities requires diverse perspectives from various disciplines and local stakeholders to ensure that these issues are effectively identified, addressed, and managed. Consequently, a transdisciplinary approach holds significant potential to enhance decision-

making, enabling Svalbard communities to navigate complex challenges and ‘balancing acts’, such as balancing environmental and economic concerns in tourism.⁴⁷

By incorporating new perspectives, transdisciplinary research in Svalbard can enhance our understanding of both problems and opportunities, benefiting research through local expertise and access to sites and funding sources. Furthermore, the involvement of non-academic stakeholders in scientific research has the potential to introduce new knowledge, perspectives, and practices, while fostering a sense of ownership and engagement in developing solutions. This is particularly crucial in Svalbard, which epitomises some of the major crises of our time. Often highlighted in the media as a climate change ‘hotspot’,⁴⁸ Svalbard attracts numerous scientists driven by the urgency of addressing these pressing challenges. Integrating non-academic actors into research can help build trust between researchers and local communities, reframing inhabitants as active agents of change rather than passive victims.⁴⁹ Nevertheless, there are significant challenges to achieving a successful transdisciplinary process. Knowledge hierarchies that typically prioritise ‘hard’ sciences over qualitative disciplines and local knowledge can lead to imbalanced power dynamics within project teams. Additionally, the meaningful inclusion of ‘stakeholders’ in research remains a challenge. In the following section, we explore the various factors that must be considered in this process.

Key considerations for conducting transdisciplinary research

Communication

Given that transdisciplinary projects bring together scientists from diverse disciplines and non-academic stakeholders with varying perspectives and goals, effective communication throughout all phases of research is crucial. For scientists, it matters how we understand and use words, recognise each other’s differences and communication styles, comprehend and respect varied research methods, and acknowledge how different forms of data are defined differently across natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities. Our discussions revealed that the most critical factors for successful collaboration are communication, the sharing of experiences and perspectives, and the establishment of a shared language. Large projects often involve scientists who may not be trained in interdisciplinary research, leading to situations where the same terms can carry different meanings across fields. This challenge becomes even more apparent when non-academic stakeholders are involved. A lack of consensus on the definitions of key terms among the parties involved may lead to confusion and disagreement. Therefore, effective and open communication among all collaborators, from the inception of a project to its completion, is an essential, albeit demanding, aspect of overcoming these challenges.

Defining non-academic ‘stakeholders’

The inclusion of non-academic stakeholders in research and the co-production of knowledge is a key aspect of transdisciplinarity. Identifying the stakeholders and defining who this refers to in a given context was emphasised by the workshop participants as

⁴⁷Hovelsrud et al. *Sustainable Tourism*, 89

⁴⁸Meyer and Sokoličková, “Melting Worlds”, 1–18.

⁴⁹Farbotko and Lazrus, *The First Climate Refugees?*, 382–390.

a primary consideration when conducting transdisciplinary research. The concept ‘stakeholder’ was not well received by many of the participants, and other terms, such as ‘actor’, ‘partner’, ‘collaborator’, ‘interest group’, and ‘knowledge holder’, were suggested as more palatable. Although the participants did not reach a consensus on which term to use, and definitions of these terms vary, they agreed that any term used in a specific context should be understood inclusively. If a ‘stakeholder’ is associated with official representatives of institutions and organisations, individuals who lack representation within these entities may be marginalised. Adding the qualifier ‘local’ does not resolve this issue, because the term becomes complex and problematic in the highly transient and multinational setting of Svalbard, where individuals cultivate ‘multiple belongings’.⁵⁰

The term ‘stakeholder’ can also lead to a sense of ‘othering’, positioning scientists apart from non-scientific ‘others’. Viewing all collaborators – scientists and non-scientists alike – as ‘knowledge holders’ who contribute diverse perspectives has the potential to recognise various knowledge systems and challenge the hierarchy that places scientific knowledge above other types of knowledge. In this context, terms such as ‘non-academic’ or ‘non-scientific’ collaborators should also be used with care because individuals classified as stakeholders may have received scientific training or work in academia but not as scientists. This discussion revealed that while the literature often presents idealised concepts of ‘stakeholders’, the Svalbard case underscores the complexity and nuance of local realities. We acknowledge that this is a contested term requiring careful consideration and definition in each project. As described above, we apply the term ‘non-academic stakeholder’ to refer to individuals and organisations who affect or are affected by the ongoing changes in Svalbard. These stakeholders may include residents, policy- and decision-makers, industry representatives, and other societal actors not necessarily located in Svalbard.

Temporal and structural challenges

Funding schemes, varying timelines for different project partners, and the overall temporal precarity of academia often leave little room for the lengthy process required to build trust between scientists and stakeholders. Funding schemes typically operate within a tight timeline, with limited time between calls and deadlines for submissions. Sufficient involvement is time-consuming, and developing a transdisciplinary project requires more flexibility throughout, including during the planning phase, than (inter)disciplinary efforts. Building trust between scientists and stakeholders and conducting pre-project consultations is necessary before the work can begin. This requires substantial time before funding is secured. Sufficient time must be allocated to allow all non-academic stakeholders to contribute to the development of a project and ensure adequate time for internal processes such as acquiring permissions and approvals.

Project work packages and deliverables are typically defined during the application stage before the research begins, which can limit flexibility and hinder the incorporation of new research questions, perspectives, and goals that may emerge during collaborations throughout the research process. When publishing research results, different disciplines often exhibit significantly different practices regarding the speed of analysis and dissemination in specialised journals. While academic results may take years to be

⁵⁰Christensen and Jensen, *Roots and Routes*, 146–155; Sokolíčková, *The Trouble with Local Community*, 1–11.

published, non-academic stakeholders often depend on and prefer the immediate delivery of results to translate them into actionable items and integrate them into their work. Furthermore, limited or insufficient planning and financial resources often result in poor timing. The workshop participants noted that researchers often arrive in Svalbard on short notice, typically during busy periods or holidays, such as during the sunny winter (snowmobile season) or summer months. As in any Arctic location, research in Svalbard must adapt to legal requirements in addition to climatic and logistical challenges. In response to ongoing climatic and political changes, environmental regulations in Svalbard are currently being tightened, which limits local recreational, tourist, and research activities. Researchers have reported that obtaining the necessary permits to conduct research activities has become increasingly difficult, both in terms of the lead time required for applications and the number of permissions granted. Certain areas are now temporarily or permanently closed to access, further restricting fieldwork. Additionally, the unique weather conditions, the remoteness of many locations, and the need for specialised equipment require careful logistical planning in the context of research in Svalbard.

Data sharing

While funding bodies increasingly advocate for data sharing within academia, the practical implementation of this process is complicated. In economic terms, data is viewed as a form of research capital that can only be shared under pre-agreed conditions. Additionally, since research is often funded by public money, there is a responsibility to ensure that the data is used appropriately and ethically. Discussions during the workshops revealed that participants from different disciplines held varying perceptions of what constitutes data. Data storage procedures can also differ among disciplines, institutions, and individual researchers. Although depositing data in an open-access system is increasingly a prerequisite for securing funding, this practice is not yet uniformly implemented across all research conducted in Svalbard. Data procured for a project is typically owned by the academic institutions employing the researchers, rather than by individual researchers or community members. In other Arctic regions, this situation is changing, with Indigenous groups reclaiming rights to data collected within and through their communities. However, this is not (yet) the case in Svalbard. Nonetheless, funding agencies such as the Research Council of Norway mandate data resulting from the projects they fund must be made openly accessible.

Within the social sciences, the sharing of qualitative data is a complex process due to ethical and legal considerations, particularly when it involves confidential data sourced from interviews or participant observation. Qualitative data must typically be accompanied by essential background information, including details about how, when, by whom, and for what purpose it was collected. Without this context, the data is prone to misinterpretation. The limited sharing of data within humanistic disciplines depends partly on our definition of 'data'. If this concept is expanded to include the knowledge artefacts customarily used in historical disciplines, for example, the Svalbard Museum emerges as an underutilised transdisciplinary 'technology of innovation' that warrants further exploration.⁵¹ Data sharing is also inherently reliant on reduction, which

⁵¹Thomas, *The Return of Curiosity*, 9

necessitates a synthesis of the research conducted. In the natural sciences, databases and data repositories have been developed over time, and while they are not yet optimal, several data-sharing platforms and hubs exist in Svalbard. The SIOS plays a crucial role in facilitating these efforts. However, functional interfaces that enable the integration of data from the natural sciences with data from the social sciences and humanities remain scarce. Data collected prior to the implementation of requirements for data accessibility may be kept private by certain gatekeepers, or there might be no access points at all, leading to what is referred to as 'lost' or 'forgotten' data.

In Svalbard, the maritime industry (e.g. AECO) follows an alternative data-sharing principle. In this model, while the academic stakeholder retains ownership of the data, the industry has immediate access to the produced work and a summary of the study results. A level of confidentiality is typically agreed upon during the proposal-writing stage. This approach allows the industry to respond swiftly to research findings, enabling them to produce internal reports and use the study results in their internal processes, such as reviewing guidelines, informing partners about developments, formulating new regulations, and adjusting their processes. It also helps non-academic stakeholders achieve their project goals within the designated timeframe.

Research fatigue

When conducting transdisciplinary research, various societal characteristics must also be considered. In Longyearbyen, research fatigue and collaboration overload have emerged as significant challenges, particularly as numerous projects converge. Researchers drawn to Svalbard due to its accessibility and established infrastructure often fail to engage with non-academic stakeholders during the early stages of project planning. A lack of thoughtful, proactive communication with non-academic stakeholders might result in discontent when they are later asked to participate in research projects. In a small community like Longyearbyen, both local scientists and non-academic stakeholders may experience task overload or over-exposure to specific projects. Insufficient communication between academic and non-academic stakeholders, coupled with the absence of well-established procedures for transdisciplinary projects, may be the reason stakeholders might become sceptical of engaging with research projects in general. Another characteristic specific to Svalbard that impacts transdisciplinary research is the high turnover rate of the population. On one hand, the influx of new arrivals continuously expands the 'pool' of potential research participants, and many newcomers express interest in learning about and participating in projects. On the other hand, the transience of the population means that few research participants have the desired expertise or long-term knowledge of the community and its environment. This transience complicates the maintenance of long-term partnerships between science and society.

'Aspects of success' or how to overcome possible challenges

The workshop participants reflected on and discussed what one participant described as the 'aspects of success' in transdisciplinary efforts.

A truly transdisciplinary approach involves identifying the relevant non-academic stakeholders and their needs during the conceptualisation of a research project, as well as collaboratively defining the research questions. To successfully include these

stakeholders, transdisciplinary projects must hold local relevance to secure their involvement. Projects that promise applicable knowledge and address locally prioritised challenges are more likely to engage stakeholders and enhance their motivation to participate. One participant noted that the gap between authorities and scientists in Longyearbyen has narrowed due to a mutual understanding of how both groups can assist and complement one another. As these two groups become better acquainted, research agendas can be developed with a clear focus on the community's needs.

To achieve meaningful engagement, workshop participants emphasised the importance of involving non-academic actors *early* in the research process. These stakeholders must be identified, contacted, and invited to collaborate *before* the research begins. Pre-proposal funding serves as an important tool for mitigating the structural challenges described above and should be allocated during open community meetings where stakeholders are invited to share their wishes and needs. Many projects rely on consultation workshops to collect community input and establish collaborations. However, consultation should be viewed as an ongoing process, and maintaining communication with stakeholders throughout the research process is essential. In Longyearbyen, leveraging existing structures, events, and institutions has proven effective in both establishing collaborations and disseminating findings. The Svalbard Science Forum functions as a key coordinating institution, fostering joint research efforts through initiatives like the RCN funding calls tailored for collaboration in Svalbard. While open meetings typically attract only a small segment of the Longyearbyen population, alternative engagement methods, such as individual meetings, should also be employed. Furthermore, stakeholders should have the opportunity to provide input and shape the research outside of formal meetings, through written contributions and co-authorship. Developing a co-created involvement strategy can help mitigate research fatigue and facilitate collaboration. This strategy should clarify the aims, expectations, and roles of partners from the outset, as well as define common goals and desired outcomes. While scientific and societal partners may have different priorities, successful collaborations are those in which mutual benefits can be identified. Defining tangible outcomes and products, such as policy briefs, at the start of the project can be a valuable exercise to ensure that diverse perspectives are incorporated and that goals are ultimately achieved. Additionally, coordinating research and dissemination activities was identified as crucial for mitigating research fatigue, highlighting the importance of utilising existing local arenas and institutions for this purpose.

Participants emphasised data sharing as a crucial yet challenging aspect of successful transdisciplinary collaboration. While data sharing among natural science projects is generally perceived as being relatively straightforward, sharing qualitative and social science data presents difficulties due to the importance of context and ethical considerations involved in gathering data from human subjects. To facilitate data sharing, creating clear descriptions of the data – addressing questions such as ‘How was it created?’ and ‘What does it mean?’ – was identified as a concrete measure. Additionally, establishing routines for data sharing within the project team from the outset was highlighted as particularly beneficial. To overcome challenges related to language and communication, especially among researchers from different disciplines, it is essential to take the time to discuss and define key terms at the outset of the project. This practice is

pivotal for success and helps avoid the loss of valuable time. Collaborative fieldwork can also be beneficial, as it allows project members to become acquainted with one another and learn about the data collection methods employed in other disciplines. Furthermore, maintaining effective communication and a good flow of information between all partners throughout the research process is crucial; relying solely on early consultation meetings and a dissemination event at the end of the project is insufficient.

In some cases, including stakeholders as full partners has proven to be highly effective. The formal involvement of partners signifies their commitment of time and effort in exchange for financial compensation. However, such involvement also requires sharing the risks associated with the project, including time constraints and potential challenges in achieving research goals. Institutionalising partnerships can help mitigate issues related to the high population turnover in Svalbard. While the formal involvement of certain institutions is straightforward, others may be ineligible to receive funding from various funding bodies, which can lead to biases in the involvement of specific stakeholders. Additionally, while compensating private individuals is common in other Arctic contexts, this practice is not prevalent in Svalbard.

Workshop participants emphasised that mutual trust among research actors is essential for successful collaboration. However, building this trust demands both time and resources. Creating opportunities for in-person meetings and communication, including informal exchanges, was emphasised as crucial. Projects that involve researchers based in Svalbard or those with the temporal and financial resources to ensure long-term community engagement tend to be more successful in establishing lasting collaborations than 'fly-in-fly-out projects' with tight schedules. Participants who had the opportunity to socialise and engage in discussions with colleagues and research partners noted that these interactions are vital for overcoming challenges related to communication, disciplinary misunderstandings, or disagreements. Furthermore, timing and planning are critical for success. Local stakeholders stressed the importance of timely planning, prompt communication with individuals, and being mindful of other important local events. Meetings should be scheduled outside of peak times and at moments when societal partners are available to facilitate effective collaboration. Additionally, it is essential to allocate time and funding for consistent follow-up procedures, as well as for the appropriate outreach and communication of results. To address the challenges posed by strict timelines and varying temporalities, project partners should agree on a timeline from the outset for delivering results, internal reports, and outreach materials.

Participants also underscored the importance of establishing dedicated spaces to foster successful partnerships and collaborations. This need became particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic when many project teams were unable to meet in person for extended periods. Creating opportunities for meetings, relationship-building, and discussions – both digitally and in person – is essential. When efforts are made to cultivate safe and comfortable environments where individuals can be open and honest, trust is strengthened, allowing collaboration to flourish. The workshop participants highlighted the need for such a space or platform to share experiences, discuss societal research needs, and develop collaborations.

Discussion

Transdisciplinarity is a method-driven scientific principle⁵² —or rather, a collection of toolkits that encompass methods guided by democratic and pragmatic principles.⁵³ The democratic principle ensures the inclusion of diverse stakeholders. The pragmatic principle entails identifying efficient ways to address real-world problems. In the following section, we will discuss our findings in light of these two principles and present a set of recommendations for advancement of transdisciplinarity in Svalbard.

Democratic principle: collaboration and integration of different types of knowledge

Ethics is a core aspect of transdisciplinary research, as the co-production of knowledge can be viewed as an emancipatory and democratic process that leads to more equitable research outcomes. Conversely, excluding certain academic disciplines or non-academic stakeholders from the transdisciplinary research process can perpetuate existing power imbalances and mechanisms of exclusion. Integrating knowledge democratically into transdisciplinary research implies considering multiple levels of governance across various locations. It also necessitates an ethical awareness of how to achieve authentic inclusion within a heterogeneous population with unequal rights. The explicit nature of Svalbard's power relations and legal frameworks serves as an exception that underscores the rule: power dynamics are an inherent dimension of any transdisciplinary research project and must, therefore, be part of its methodological starting point.

In our own process of facilitating workshops, we encountered specific ethical dilemmas regarding inclusion, particularly concerning which stakeholders to invite and the locations for the workshops. The funding call for these workshops was linked to the Svalbard Science Conference in Oslo and the Arctic Congress Bodø 2024. However, we recognised that these locations favoured the participation of researchers while likely presenting obstacles for some stakeholders based in Svalbard. Although a range of local stakeholders participated, this limitation must be acknowledged in our study.

Furthermore, while existing studies primarily highlight the importance of involving stakeholders in knowledge production,⁵⁴ our transdisciplinary approach and findings underscored the value of extending the democratic principle to the development of methods. Based on our positive experience with the conducted workshops, we recommend integrating stakeholders not only in the 'doing' of transdisciplinary knowledge production but also in the conceptual and methodological stages of 'thinking' about how this process can be most effectively designed. Our findings indicate that stakeholders' experiences of both 'doing' and 'thinking' within a transdisciplinary methodology have the potential to foster a sense of ownership and partnership amongst participants. This, in turn, could enhance overall research quality and lay the foundation for building social capital and a shared commitment to addressing common challenges.

⁵²Lang et al., *Transdisciplinary Research*, 25–43.

⁵³Laursen et al., *Toolkitting*.

⁵⁴Brandt et al., *A Review of Transdisciplinary Research*, 1–15; Angelstam et al., *Solving Problems*, 254–65.

Including stakeholders in discussions about how best to conduct transdisciplinary research in Svalbard revealed both challenges and benefits that extend beyond those identified by the researchers. This inclusive process allowed us to uncover and engage with stakeholders' perspectives on which societally relevant problems are suitable for transdisciplinary research, as well as their views on the challenges and benefits of participating in such projects. We find that incorporating stakeholders' perspectives – not only on what to study but also on *how* to study it – is essential for advancing the development of transdisciplinary methodologies. Our experience throughout this process has also highlighted the importance of transparency regarding ethical dilemmas and the understanding that choices made to address these dilemmas inevitably come with limitations. Ethical transparency is an integral part of transdisciplinarity as a methodology and should be considered in all transdisciplinary projects. We observed how establishing a democratic transdisciplinary space can create favourable conditions for co-reflection, knowledge co-creation and dissemination, and mutual understanding of the needs of different stakeholders.

Trust, recognition, participation, and local ownership are cornerstones of transdisciplinary methodology,⁵⁵ yet building these bonds and bridges demands time and engagement before a research project can begin. A transdisciplinary approach reminds researchers that, although they have expertise within their own scientific disciplines, local stakeholders possess relevant expert knowledge of the local context. We find that funding agencies have a key ethical responsibility to invest in pre-proposal funding that enables researchers to create favourable conditions for a democratic, transdisciplinary process. This finding suggests that funding agencies will play an important role in the future development and application of transdisciplinary methodologies, implying a change to their standard practices.

Pragmatic principle: how to effectively solve real-world 'wicked problems'

A transdisciplinary approach aims to identify and implement solutions, or transitions, for wicked problems⁵⁶ concerning humans' interrelationships with nature. The pragmatic principle underlying transdisciplinarity resembles the logic of a crystal ball – it aims to foresee the potential challenges that lie ahead and to prepare for them. Our study confirms this principle. Workshop discussions suggested that relational barriers to partnerships and collaborations – such as conflicts of interest, friction, miscommunication, and potential disciplinary dominance – can be addressed early on by establishing routines for transparency, dialogue, and initial agreement on evaluation criteria and the definitions of concepts. Timely recognition of practical barriers, such as regulatory constraints and data sharing limitations, can be valuable when developing platforms for shared access and tailoring them to users' needs.

Our findings indicate that data sharing is a precondition for the successful realisation of the transdisciplinary approach. However, data sharing emerges as a particularly complex process, even in Svalbard. In addition to questions of access, the appropriate timing for data sharing is crucial, as data may become outdated before it is properly published.

⁵⁵Polk, *Transdisciplinary Co-Production*, 110–122.

⁵⁶Lang et al., *Transdisciplinary Research*, 25–43.

Data sharing exemplifies how transdisciplinarity requires platforms that transcend traditional institutional structures.⁵⁷ The risks, needs, and complexities involved in data sharing represent important aspects of transdisciplinary research that funding agencies must consider when designing their calls, especially for projects involving participants from multiple countries.

Our results indicate that mobility, geographic location, degree of involvement, and sense of belonging are intertwined phenomena that complicate the question of who qualifies as a relevant stakeholder, especially since this answer may change over time. Although the turnover rate in Longyearbyen is exceptional, increasing human mobility – both within and across borders – is an underlying dimension of many transdisciplinary research projects and warrants further attention. Our findings suggest the value of creating a platform for transdisciplinary knowledge and expertise tied to a specific location. This is especially relevant to transdisciplinary projects aimed at democratic and efficient collaborations in other hypermobile environments, such as among NGOs and in settlements experiencing simultaneous and heterogeneous migration flows, which are now occurring in other Arctic locations. However, the lessons we have learned indicate that such a location-specific repository or ‘memory bank’ is not merely a static toolkit to be opened on demand and then closed again; it must be a dynamic forum, a space for dialogue that remains a ‘work in progress’, where the conditions for transdisciplinarity are as important as the contents of the toolkit.

Transdisciplinary toolkit repositories and even meta-alliances between them are now gaining attention due to their potential for achieving real-world impact.⁵⁸ We have learned that establishing a forum where participants can co-reflect on transdisciplinary methods can contribute to identifying participants’ primary objectives and foreseeing challenges regarding future projects. Since transdisciplinarity incorporates the voices of those directly affected, such methodological co-reflection must be adapted to each context and grounded in the lived realities of various stakeholders. This anchoring and ownership leads to a greater likelihood of project outcomes being accepted and implemented.⁵⁹

The transdisciplinary approach can inform regulations that balance environmental protection with economic activities, such as mining or tourism, ensuring that policies are evidence-based and reflect the priorities of both local and global stakeholders. For example, collaboration between researchers and the tourism industry can lead to sustainable tourism that reconciles ecological preservation with economic benefits, which is critical for long-term sustainability. Hence, transdisciplinarity can be considered not only as a research methodology but also as a vision, a practice, and a strategic tool for fostering effective, transparent, and democratic decision-making in complex contexts.

Learning from the Svalbard context

Transdisciplinary projects will be fundamental in creating effective relationships across scientific disciplines and between academic and non-academic stakeholders

⁵⁷Thompson et al., *Scientist and Stakeholder*, 30–39.

⁵⁸Laursen et al., *Toolkitting*.

⁵⁹Hummel, *Inter- and Transdisciplinary*, 481–509.

Figure 2. Recommendations for transdisciplinary research in Svalbard.

in Svalbard. By adopting a transdisciplinary approach, we can produce research that advances knowledge while delivering tangible benefits for society and the environment. Although the results of this study are specific to the context of Svalbard, they hold relevance for other Arctic locations as *general principles*. Based on our study findings, we offer recommendations that outline a way forward for transdisciplinary research in Svalbard (Figure 2).

Identify and Involve Diverse Stakeholders. Map the potential participants whose perspectives should be integrated, ensuring representation from diverse actors, including typically underrepresented groups like non-Norwegian residents. Co-create a research agenda that emerges from local realities and priorities. Avoid one-size-fits-all models; instead, apply transferable principles tailored to the specific context of Svalbard.

Enhance Transdisciplinary Capacity. Researchers should be equipped with the necessary skills to navigate disciplinary differences in language, methodology, and assumptions, as well as specific training in the ‘nuts and bolts’ of the transdisciplinary toolkit and process. Use existing networks focused on transdisciplinary tools and processes in the Svalbard context, allowing for knowledge and experience to be shared among researchers and practitioners.

Address Structural and Temporal Challenges. Acknowledge constraints such as funding timelines and limited resources, which can hinder trust-building among disciplines

and local communities. Combat research fatigue by fostering trust and avoiding attitudes of ‘othering’ that alienate residents and collaborators.

Establish Data-Sharing Protocols. Define data-sharing practices early on, balancing the interests of funding bodies and stakeholders. Promote data sharing across disciplines and with non-academic participants to build a shared knowledge base that benefits both science and society.

Learn from Successful Practices. Incorporate proven strategies, such as 1) establishing a communication strategy; 2) early stakeholder involvement; 3) flexible project frameworks including the interests and goals of all partners; 4) allocating adequate time for all participants to navigate their internal processes and contribute meaningfully to the collaboration; 5) tailored data-sharing formats across disciplines; 6) follow-up routines and adequate dissemination practices (e.g. reports and presentations for non-academic users); 7) spaces for self-reflection and open discussions within the project team.

Distinguish Research from Consultancy. Maintain methodological rigour by adhering to FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability) in scientific practice. Clearly define the boundaries between transdisciplinary research and consultancy to preserve the integrity of the research process.

Leverage Existing Networks and Platforms. Utilise organisations like the Svalbard Science Forum (SSF), the Svalbard Social Science Initiative, and the University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS) to connect researchers and non-academic stakeholders, reducing research fatigue and fostering collaboration. Maintain such platforms to support dialogue, knowledge-sharing, and methodology development specific to Svalbard.

When steps are made transparent and we share our lessons learned, we begin to assemble an expert ‘toolkit’ for transdisciplinary methodology within the Svalbard context.⁶⁰ This marks the beginning of the work to build transdisciplinary bridges.

Conclusions

Transdisciplinary research is emerging as an essential framework for addressing wicked problems. This approach offers immense potential for addressing Svalbard’s coupled socio-environmental challenges within its unique legal frameworks. Furthermore, it contributes to addressing important knowledge gaps, coordinating resources, presenting recommendations to governments, providing knowledge for effective policymaking, addressing barriers and identifying pathways for successful transdisciplinary research. The results of this qualitative inquiry confirm the importance of developing sound transdisciplinary research methodologies and the necessity of creating a platform to facilitate transdisciplinary research. However, a primary limitation of the scope of the study is the lack of explicit comparison to the broader Arctic context.

The results of our study align with some of the broader concerns surrounding transdisciplinary methodology, particularly the potential for conflicting interests and differing expectations between academic and non-academic stakeholders. The credibility of the methodology hinges on whether stakeholders in the Svalbard context can establish effective communication, a common language, and a mutual understanding of their respective needs. Through co-reflection, project stakeholders can work towards a shared vision. Additionally,

⁶⁰Laursen et al., *Toolkitting*.

reaching an agreement on common normative guidelines for the transdisciplinary process is a prerequisite for cooperation and co-creation of knowledge among stakeholders.

We identify a clear need for a transdisciplinary platform to facilitate research in Svalbard that transcends traditional institutional structures and allows for the assessment and learning from efforts to integrate methodologies and methods from various disciplines and non-academic stakeholders. Such a platform can also offer recommendations and support the ongoing development of a transdisciplinary methodology tailored to the Svalbard context, with principles that may be applicable to similar transdisciplinary projects in other Arctic regions. The dialogue initiated in the workshops leading to the development of this paper is a step in this direction. An important avenue for further research emerged during the analysis: in the context of Svalbard, the distinction between scientific and non-academic stakeholders does not reflect fundamentally different cosmologies. This observation has significant implications for how we conceptualise the co-production of knowledge and merits deeper investigation.

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